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BEMServer And Occupant Behaviour: A New Approach Towards Addressing The Energy Gap in Buildings

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Abstract

The actual energy consumption of buildings in Europe often exceeds design energy predictions by a significant margin. This gap between actual energy performance and design energy performance can arise from construction errors, commissioning errors and/or the way buildings are actually used. Moreover, occupant behaviour is now widely recognized as a major contributing factor to this gap. HIT2GAP is a Horizon 2020 EU-funded project that seeks to reduce the gap between predicted and actual energy consumption of buildings. To do this, HIT2GAP develops an energy management platform (BEMServer) which could eliminate this gap in existing buildings, by providing a data platform, energy predictions and benchmarks as well as modules that address the concerns of facility and energy managers. This study presents the BEMServer and the semantic driven behaviour module that is developed within the HIT2GAP project. The architecture of the BEMServer as well as the behaviour module's functionalities, the outputs and the use cases are provided.

Keywords: Energy management, Occupant behavior, Data platform.